

Examining the Impact of Employee Relations on Employee Retention in the Context of Higher Education Institutes (HEI)

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Abstract : *Employee relations are one of the critical essential components of hierarchical execution, success, and maintainability. Enviably employee relations result in profoundly dedicated, propelled, and steadfast workers in the associations. Keeping up with and encouraging great relations between employers and employees can make an amicable air. Invariability at work not only aids in protecting the interests of employers and employees but also advances the dynamic improvement of the association. To guarantee the supportability of amicable employee relations, endeavors to fortify these two gatherings should be offered consideration. Employee relations that target laying out and keeping a warm association among employees and the organization, directors, and among employees have been at the focal point of consideration as far back as a decade. The adverse consequences of employer-employee relations, an employer who neglects to comprehend issues concerning his employees probably won't make long-term progress in his undertaking.*

Employee turnover is a significant issue in higher education that can result in a deficiency of ability and experience, diminished efficiency, and inflated costs for enrollment and new staff preparation. The literature suggests that the primary factors contributing to the high rate of employee turnover among employees working in higher education are low salaries and benefits, a lack of career growth opportunities, a well-balanced work life, poor leadership, and a lack of communication. Many academic employees are concerned about leaving their current employers because of these factors,

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which can result in a lack of career fulfillment, and inspiration, and a sense of career stagnation.

In light of the fact that employees are the most important resource for any organization, this study aims to investigate and analyze a literature review on employee retention strategies of higher education institutions. It aims to determine the factors influencing and attempting to quantify employee retention. In this review, the sample was gathered from different employees of various higher education institutes situated in Lucknow, by a self-regulated questionnaire based on the random sampling method (RSM). The assessment was done by quantifiable assessments in SPSS. The study's findings confirm that higher education institutions (HEI) need to foster areas of strength between management and employees, establish a decent open climate, and urge representatives to fill in collectively without segregation. Additionally, this paper gives bits of knowledge into the difficulties faced by institutes in retaining their academic employees and the need to carry out methodologies to further improve retention. Besides, this study likewise gives different suggestions to the top administration of the colleges to give regard alongside worth and appreciation, give a sound workplace and occupation configuration, place employees as per their abilities, and give vocation valuable learning experiences to retain a quality workforce by making them committed and secured. Accordingly, higher education institutions can lessen the expenses related to employee turnover and affirm that they have experienced and talented employees to convey high-quality education and research. Additionally, future recommendations have been made for researchers who are interested in the subject.

Keywords : Employee Relation, Employee Retention, Higher Education Institutes, Employer, Employee.

1. Introduction

Employees are among an organization's most valuable assets and are reckoned as one of its most valuable assets. An organization's productivity is directly influenced by its nature and volume of work. Affiliations cannot perform better and achieve their objectives if there is a horrendous association between employees and employers. Consequently, fostering healthy relationships with employees inside an association is essential for any association to develop and succeed. Maintaining and facilitating healthy relationships with employees are

imperative to the workplace whether an employee is hired, stays with the company, or leaves the organization (Rose, 2008). Great employer-employee relations are fundamental for the association since they animate employees to work better and produce more outcomes (Burns, 2012). The organization persistently endeavors to keep up with concordance, inspiration, dedication, and fulfillment among their employees to guarantee consistent development and tranquil working of the endeavor. Job satisfaction of employees is fundamental for the retention of key and significant workers of an association. Subsequently, understanding the possibility of the employer-employee relationship and supporting this relationship is incredibly central to the organization. Dealing with this relationship is crucial to business achievement, as a strong relationship can incite more prominent employee satisfaction and, surprisingly, expanded efficiency. Thus, an organization can additionally foster execution when the employees that work with that organization have cultivated a sensation of belonging, and contribute to the prosperity of the organization.

Employers supplementary view and consider employee relation virtuosity and capabilities as a crucial and fundamental essential element to accomplish and ameliorate the consummation of their organization which makes the employers revolve more around the contribution, commitment, obligation, and performance of employees to escalate the overall productiveness of their organization. In this manner, the employer-employee relation is a premeditated tool of the administration while managing hierarchical risks.

In 1977, Dunlop expressed that an industrial relation framework, which contains factors, for instance, employees, employers, and under specific conditions, for example, political, financial, social, and so on concludes the workplace state of play, environment, conditions, rules and their operation functions. Furthermore, the working environment of the organization in which the employees effectuate their operations likewise significantly affects the employer and employee relation of an organization. Consequently, the administration of the organization must consider the different dispositions, dynamics, and factors inside and outside the organization to conclude its performance and consistency in its improvement level in this vicious world.

The various aspects of how people interact at work are the focus of employee relations. Employee relations, subsequently, is the correspondence between employees themselves and their employers. Such correspondence can either be formal or informal. It envelops all areas of management that might incorporate work relations, employee inclusion and cooperation, employee correspondence, and industrial relations (Armstrong, 2008).

Academic employee turnover has transformed into a pertinent predicament all over the world. Retention of employees is a perplexity for Higher Education Institutions (HEI). The high turnover rate of academic staff can extensively affect understudies and remaining staff individuals when void positions exist considering a shortfall of accessible qualified faculty (Selesho and Naile, 2014). A survey conducted by The Chronicle of Higher Education figured out that fifty percent of academic staff members reported that their enjoyment of teaching had diminished over the year during the pandemic that forced the transition to online teaching (Din et al., 2023). According to Din et al. (2023), the reasons for this decline include concerns about reduced salaries, job security, increased workload, and the pressures brought on by remote work arrangements. In an equal vein, a different article shared a comparative point of view, demonstrating that roughly, 35% of Higher Education Institutions (HEI) were contending with employee turnover, and more than 55% of these establishments were defied with the test of experienced and talented academic staff individual's people considering leaving the workforce. In addition, the article featured that a significant 70% of the general academic staff had encountered uplifted pressure because of their heavy workloads over the preceding year (Umpierrez, 2021). These predicaments inclusively highlight the exigent for the global higher education sector to ameliorate and inflate employees' job satisfaction; the inability to do so could overburden the sector (Din et al., 2023).

Within the confines of the higher education environment, high employee turnover adversely influences understudies' accomplishment, and learning opens doors (Garibay, 2015). To surmount such sort of issues colleges and universities need to focus on their commitments to educating and learning, need to make the indispensable efforts to hold their skilled and talented labor force and such staff should be spurred to work effectively (Selesho et al., 2014). With such earnest endeavors, the purpose of colleges and universities to confer quality training in the public arena can be accomplished.

Even though hierarchical pioneers cannot thoroughly obliterate employee turnover, they can perpetrate employee retention strategies and methodologies to diminish employee turnover (Garibay, 2015; Sandhya and Kumar, 2014). Compelling employee retention strategies should be an effort that is precise by the businesses to such an extent that an environment is created that urges the current staff to remain utilized with the assistance of specific arrangements and legit rehearses that satisfy their ambitions. In the present period stable labor force enjoys a competitive advantage for an organization in light of the fact that a changing labor force needs higher consumption on the enlistment and training

process. A consistent workforce will make more grounded educator-student associations and understudies can have the advantage of the educator insight because of the progression of their subject information, intensity of institution experience, and corroborated performance (Kreisman, 2002).

2. Employee Relations and Employee Retention

The term 'employee relations' alludes to an organization's endeavors to regulate associations between employers and employees. Employee relations are conventionally oriented with regulating dealing with the business relationship and fostering a positive mental understanding. Employee relations incorporate the assortment of work concerned with nurturing employer-employee relationships that add efficiency, inspiration, and confidence. Employee relations is mostly managing the inner connection between the employer and employee in an association, this inner relationship is centered around speculations of the human way of behaving (Liao et al., 2004). Subsequently, it might be portrayed as the association between the employer and employees or the business and delegates or, pointed towards creating certainty, trust, and a valuable and great work environment (Bajaj et al., 2013). Employee relations partake in an unrivaled working environment for representative viability, work fulfillment, support, worker execution, strength, commitment, upkeep, and so on, to stay away from any further employer-employee-related issues. It sets out areas of strength to different degrees of progress and evaluations of the other variables influencing the business. Fundamentally, employee relations focus is stressed over thwarting and settling issues including individuals, which arise out of or affect work conditions. It concerns the relationship of workers with the association and one another. It integrates the patterns of creating, executing, regulating, and investigating the employer-employee relationship, overseeing worker execution, and settling working environment clashes/debates. Employers need to direct associations in the workplace to keep the business working easily, stay away from issues, and ensure representatives are performing at their best. Therefore, the term employee relations implies characterizing the association between employers and employees.

When a manager takes the time to build relationships with employees and direct them to produce more high-quality work, the employees' effectiveness and productivity are directly correlated. A cohesive group can be formed through strong, sensitive leadership and the development of good relationships with employees. It is the most effective strategy for closing the productivity gap between employees. (Chapman & Goodwin, 2001).

Despite its straightforward understanding, retention can be more difficult to accomplish. In general, it is an arduous process. It is a good start to know what employees want and need. To keep their most valuable and talented employees, managers must acknowledge and accept that they are responsible for managing the factors within their control (Pavithra & Thirukumaran, 2018). In addition, when a worker characterizes their career options, managers are likely to reevaluate their methodology to retain committed and significant employees to the association (Coetzee et al., 2015). Intelligent employers always recognize the significance of retaining the best employees. In the global context and India, talent retention has been crucial. Similarly, Sepahvand and Khodashahri (2021) explained that human resources (HR) are essential to intellectual capital and one of an organization's most valuable assets. Because of the shortage of experienced and talented human resources(HR), enlisting and retaining great quality workers for the long haul is pivotal.

An employee who is persuaded and content with their employer is more likely to want to stay with the company for a long time. In this circumstance, management must exert additional effort to retain valuable employees. According to Wulansari et al. (2020), worker turnover results in a significant loss of capital and efficiency; this could be avoided by shaping compelling human resource (HR) systems and strategies to hold a quality labor force. Further, he expressed that the administration ought to draw in its talented representatives by giving them a serviceable and open climate. To ensure that it can retain its human capital, management should also provide a convenient and comfortable work environment, welfare benefits, a solid salary structure, job security, and other benefits (Wulansari et al., 2020). Retaining employees is also important because it helps the company achieve its larger goals and objectives while also making the organization more efficient. If a representative is engrossed and committed to their work, it would be profoundly useful regarding authoritative viability (Long, 2016).

According to Ng'ethe JM (2012), public universities operate in a highly competitive environment, necessitating employee retention to stay ahead of the competition. The exceptional idea of universities anticipates that they should be stores of the most specialized and skilled intelligent people. They hold knowledge that can be used to meet the nation's manpower requirements. The quality and quantity of faculty members influence university education. Accordingly, higher education institutions (HEI) are subject to the insightful and inventive capacities and responsibilities of the academic staff than most other associations. This makes it fundamentally imperative to hold this framework of staff (Ng'ethe JM, 2012,

Michael O et al., 2013). According to Sinniah et al. (2019), academic staff members at colleges and universities are more likely to forage for possible innovative employment alternatives than to linger to stay in their current positions. The reason is its conjunction with job satisfaction. According to Sinniah et al. (2019), several factors, including pay, advancement opportunities, the workplace, and recognition, influence faculty job satisfaction. Faculty members are more likely to leave their organization if they believe they are not receiving fair performance reviews, receive inadequate training, or are underpaid. The retention of high-performing staff is extremely significant for higher education institutions (HEI). However, industry competition makes it difficult for institutions to retain employees. According to Jointer (2012), many nations are now concerned with this situation.

3. Review of Literature

1. As per a review led by Alshamrani et al., 2023, it was exhibited that there exists a positive connection between employee retention and six key variables. These variables incorporate compensation and benefits, workplace environment, relationship with accomplices, corporate culture, employee encouragement and motivation, and leadership inside the association.
2. According to **Justice Solomon Kolantwi Barimah (2017)**, leadership and institutional culture, growth opportunities, valuable learning experiences, the institution's mission and vision, reasonable work, and collegiality influence the retention of the university's teaching employees. These formal retention strategies support the intrinsic needs of employees and furthermore leverage the qualities and strengths of their institutional culture.
3. In their article, **Mohammed Sahedur Rahman and Rabeya Khatun Taniya (2017)** emphasized that Employee Relationship Management (ERM) emphasizes novel means of communication. Both the employer and employee gain from maintaining positive employee relations. The purpose of the study was to determine how Employee Relationship Management (ERM) affects the performance of banking sector employees. The authors used HR Practices, Trust, Communication, Leadership Style, Shared Goals, and Values were used in the study by the authors. This study confirmed that Employee Relationship Management (ERM) components have a positive effect on performance. They argued that recognizing Employee Relationship Management (ERM) practices in all aspects of an organization's employees' lives would directly boost its performance.

4. **Pamuditha and Harshani Samarasinghe (2017)** in an article concentrated on three factors, including, correspondence, grievance handling, and guiding as the variables deceiving Employee Relationship Management (ERM), and figured out its effect on the inspiration of associate-level employees in a hotel in Columbo. They discovered that relations between employers and employees are poor, so they proposed some suggestions in their article to improve relations between employers and employees, focusing on the aforementioned factors.
5. As stated by **R. Anbu Ranjith Kumar (2016)** colleges employ inadequate retention policies to retain faculty members. There is a divergent workforce populace, whose solicitations effectual retention measures enhance work satisfaction, which subsequently augments work execution.
6. **Rowland Worlu et al.'s (2016)** research aims to determine whether employee relations strategies influence employee performance at a Nigerian educational institution. Factors such as versatile progressive techniques, affirmation, value, progress, and instruction influence definitive execution with the mediating elements of delegate affiliation and support. It was found that techniques for employee relations affected representatives' performance. They suggested to policymakers that a more supportive employee relations strategy would lead to increased job performance and employee retention. They called managers to focus on various versatile leveled procedures.
7. According to **Dr.Mita Mehta, Aarti Kurbetti, Ravneeta Dhankhar (2014)**, employee retention and commitment are affected by career development opportunities, compellingtalent management methodologies, enrollment, onboarding and orientation, compensatory benefits, training & development, equilibrium in work and life, authoritative culture, direction, corporate altruism, independence and emancipation, audits, individual causes, business-related techniques and leisure time, valuating performance and career developmental opportunities show the magnitude and significance on exerting influence on retention and stimulate employee obligation in the association.

4. Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate the existing academic staff retention strategies of higher education institutions in Lucknow.

2. To concentrate on the significance of retaining talented and experienced academic staff members.
3. To determine the issues and difficulties that institutes face when implementing and maintaining employee relations.
4. To proffer admonishment to overcome various obstacles and implement employee relations in institutions.

5. Statement of the Problem

Employees are regarded as the company's assets because they contribute in numerous ways to the organization's success. As a result, positive employee relations must be maintained within the organization by management. Employee relations are vital and assume a significant part in this way today the association contributes both time and money for a decent relationship in the association. The company currently faces difficulties in long-term employee retention. In this way, examining employee relation management is significant.

Stemmed from the literature review, numerous studies on employee retention have been conducted from both the employee's and employer's perspectives. There is a lack of research on the association between the reasons employees want to stay with an organization and the employer's retention strategies. The majority of studies on staff retention in the IT sector, secondary and high schools, nursing, and other fields were conducted in established businesses. As a result, there is much room for research into employee retention strategies in higher education institutions. Few studies examined the relationship between employee relations factors and strategy and employee retention.

6. Need / Significance of the Study

Employees are the quintessence of any association. Employee retention refers to an organization's strategies for maintaining employees on the staff for a long time. Employee retention strategies help employees perform their jobs well and stay with the company for a long time. To ensure that employees enjoy their work and gain knowledge, certain beneficial actions must be taken. Employee turnover is expensive for associations. It is difficult to find key employees suitable replacements. An organization's outstanding performance is correlated with low employee turnover. Thus, hiring is a challenging task. It is plausible that he will join the rivals after resigning. An employee who stays with the company for a long time is more likely to be honest with management and the organization.

The fact that employees and management play such a significant role in an organization makes this study unique. The study is expected to be beneficial to institute management, employees, staff, and future researcher management.

1. It will assist the institute in determining ways to improve employee relations. It gives useful information about employee relations that can be used in future scientific studies.
2. To the researcher, it can add to developing the researcher's information and comprehension of the part of employee relations by giving attention to the higher education institutes (HEI) about employee relations and how it exerts influence on employee retention.
3. For the employees, it will help them learn how to communicate with one another within the institute, which will make their work less stressful and teach them how to complete it more effectively and efficiently.

7. Employee Turnover in Higher Education Institutes (HEI)

In higher education institutions (HEI), administrators, academic employees, and faculty are now considered social norms (Figueroa, 2015). According to Takawira, Coetzee, and Schreuder (2014), employee turnover also significantly affected their physical, mental, and emotional well-being. Employee turnover also had an impact on higher education institution (HEI) university presidents. University presidents are powerless against instinctive and intentional turnovers. Eckel and Kezar (2016) conjectured that university presidents assume critical roles in raising money, budget management, strategic premeditation, working with the local community, state, and administering sheets, and working with executives in a tight spot. According to Figueroa (2015), employee turnover in higher education institutions (HEI) can have a negative impact on staff, faculty, and institution operations. According to Abubakar et al., 7.7% of full-time faculty members from various colleges and universities are transferred to other institutions. More than 20,000 specialists, including medical personnel and academic employees from various universities and colleges, consistently pass on to the African central area to look for work in different countries (Abubakar et al., 2015).

8. Factors of Employee Relation to Embolden Employee Retention

In light of the preceding literature review, several factors have been identified that have the potential to encourage academic employee retention. Rewards and compensation, training, working conditions, recognition, promotion, job

security, support from supervisors, job autonomy, and job satisfaction are all examples of these factors.

8.1. Rewards and Remuneration

Remuneration of representatives is essential for compensation. The term “rewards” alludes to the monetary financial, nonfinancial, and mental rewards that an organization provides to its employees in exchange for the work they perform. Reward (or compensation) management is the epicenter of employment relationships. The retention rate is inversely proportional to pay, with lower pay resulting in a higher turnover rate. The impact of pay on employee retention has been the subject of previous research (Hinkin & Tracey, 2010). Remuneration and well-being have always been important factors for faculty retention. According to Huang and Kleiner (2005), organizations use rewards and recognition to reward employees for better job performance. According to Hsieh and Kleiner (2003), reward and recognition generally have three main constructs: reward predicated on compensation, reward predicated on indirect compensation, and reward predicated on incentives. According to Chiekiezie, Emejulu, & Nwanneka (2017), retaining talented employees within an organization is engendered by putting good policies into place for reward and compensation. However, the requirements of each worker must not be verified. On this account, with the intent that businesses retain their employees, they need to understand what they want in terms of compensation and rewards. Dissatisfied lecturers are willing to relocate to universities with higher compensation packages, as the number of universities increases. According to Radhakrishnan et al. (2016), a deficiency of integrity and equity in compensation satisfaction can lead to an increase in turnover intention among academic employees. Academic employees typically experience dissatisfaction when they believe that their compensation is unfair.

8.2. Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

The human resources (HR) responsible for the institute’s expansion should be developed for the institution to grow. There is a lot to learn when teachers first start their careers. As a result, continuing professional development (CPD) is a prerequisite during the underlying years and educators have numerous opportunities to foster their knowledge, skills, and practices. Continuing professional development (CPD) opportunities that are beneficial to more experienced and accomplished educators are less common. Continuous professional development (CPD) training enables educators to succeed professionally, learn about cutting-edge new approaches, and remain up to date

on the latest trends. The best academic employees will be thrilled to stay at their current institution because they see this opportunity as a boost to their professional development. Career and professional development opportunities appear to have a strong positive correlation with employee retention, according to a previous study (Rahaman et al., 2023). Career opportunities have a significant impact on employee loyalty and retention within the organization because employees place a high value on long-term career development (Rahaman et al., 2023).

8.3. Transparency in Communication

Cultivating the relationship between employers and employees ameliorates open correspondence all through the association on a wide scale premise and at an individual level. Transparency in correspondence about the working environment rehearses accomplishes the ideal results for the worker and the association. Regular and transparent imparting of the right data to authoritative individuals on the work necessities empowers representatives to do the right things; this keeps up with trust, assembles, and attracts a workforce. This makes it easier for employees to understand expectations, objectives, and targets and how their commitments have an effect.

According to Chinomona and Sandada (2013), employees' job satisfaction is influenced by their communication transparency. Employees can work more effectively and grow as a result of improved communication, which also benefits the organization. As indicated by Debaawy (2011), correspondence and occupational fulfillment have a positive connection. Transparency in correspondence brings about the work fulfillment of representatives.

8.4. Gratifying a Healthy Work-life Balance

According to Bashir & Ramay (2008), work-life policies increase employee commitment, which in turn increases retention. People tend to be more productive when they believe their work-life balance is valued. A healthy work-life balance aids employees' mental and physical well-being. Healthier employees are more enticed, more likely to stay with the company, and less likely to take sick leave. A fundamental component of a generally successful workplace is a balance between personal life and work. It can lessen pressure and forestall burnout in the work environment, which can have adverse results on the physical and emotional well-being of their representatives. Improving employees' work-life balance can substantially reduce issues such as fatigue, low performance, mood swings, irritability, and a toxic work environment. A lot of work and

obligations influence the individual life adversely and affect retention adversely. Supplementary identified determinants that are not business concomitant like burnout, unscheduled working, and occupation stress inhibit Work-Life Balance and adversely influence retention (Mitchell et. al., 2011).

One of the main reasons teachers leave school, according to the Department of Education, is a heavy workload. For the teachers' mental, emotional, and physical well-being, it is essential to hire more teachers so that the load is distributed and the number of teaching sessions per teacher is balanced. Additionally, teachers should have small breaks to unwind and get ready for the next class.

8.5. Appealing Management and Leadership

To keep employees happy and satisfied, management and leadership need to be at their best. According to Goleman (2000), leaders who exhibit emotional intelligence, offer advice, and truly care about the well-being of their staff can foster a sense of loyalty and dedication. As per Bass and Riggio (2006), managers who effectively empower their colleagues, give them standard analysis, and give them dynamic power help to increment standards for dependability. According to Harris et al. (2016), there was a strong correlation between job satisfaction and leadership, which affected whether an employee stayed with the company or left.

Bateh and Heyliger (2014) inspected the effect that the three authority styles had on the work fulfillment of employees in a state university framework. Bateh and Heyliger (2014) deduced in their review the accompanying: (a) employees who distinguished transformational leadership as authoritative encountered an expansion in work fulfillment, (b) employees who distinguished transactional leadership as predominant likewise encountered an expansion in work fulfillment, and (c) employees who perceived detached or avoidant leadership as prevailing experience a decline in work fulfillment.

9. Research Methodology

9.1. Research Design

This study aimed to ascertain how employee relations influence employee retention in the academic sector of Lucknow. To empirically speculate on the research objective, a quantitative approach to a descriptive research design will be utilized for this study. Relevant data and information were gathered, evaluated, and analyzed using a variety of statistical tools. The study constructs— salary, promotion, recognition, and working environment— were assessed using

a five-point Likert scale, with 1 representing strongly disagree and 5 representing strongly agree. The validity and reliability of this scale are very high.

9.2. Sample and Sample Size

The study is descriptive owing to the fact that the review forages for the variables that impact employee retention in an institute. Additionally, it intends to investigate the implications of these variables for the academic staff to remain in the same foundation. The academic staff will be asked for their input through a synoptic and well-organized questionnaire. According to Wellman and Kruger (2004), a sample has the accompanying components:

- Representivity: The populace should be addressed by the sample.
- If the researcher can present their findings to that populace, the sample needs to be of a size that makes sense.
- The acceptable sample size should generally be 33% of the designated population, though sometimes 25% is sufficient. T
- The sample's randomness: Any member of the population can be part of the sample.

According to Blaikie (2018), researchers frequently choose their sample sizes by referring to sample sizes from previous research review evidence. Using a case study approach, Amena (2017) interviewed five banking managers to investigate strategies for reducing employee turnover. To ascertain how employee relationships affect employee retention in Lucknow's academic sector, 110 respondents were surveyed.

9.3. Participants

According to DeJonckheere and Vaughn (2019), participants in a review ought to have encountered or participated in the peculiarity. Therefore, to accomplish the objectives of a study, it is essential to establish selection criteria for participants (Saxena, 2017). To be eligible, participants had to be employed in higher education and have worked for more than five years. The researcher can get in touch with the institution gatekeeper at the research site to find out if participants are available and how to contact them (Fusch & Ness, 2015). To ascertain how employee relationships affect employee retention in Lucknow's academic sector, 110 respondents were surveyed.

9.4. Data Collection

- A) **Primary Data** : A structured questionnaire-based survey has been adapted for data collection.
- B) **Secondary Data** : Diversified national international journals on Staff support, maintenance and retention Frameworks, Human resource praxis to retain talented and experienced employees, retention of employees and staff in divergent areas such as the academic sector, IT areas, hospitals, enterprises, analyzing the effect of the workplace, incentives, and fringe benefits, positions of authority, research papers, proposal, and different auxiliary information sources has been utilized for the review.

Table 9.4.1 Factor measurement

Variables	No of items	Source
Rewards and Remuneration	6	Frye <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Professional development	5	Presbitero <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Communication	3	Kundu and Lata, 2017
Work-Life Balance	4	Fletcher <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Leadership	6	Kundu and Lata, 2017
Employee retention	6	Haldorai, <i>et al.</i> , 2019

9.5. Data Analysis Tool

First, the responses are placed into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 to analyze the data. Then, SPSS and Microsoft Excel were utilized to sort, dissect, and decipher the information. The reliability of data has been attempted through Cronbach Alpha. It has additionally been analyzed through descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics like frequencies, percentages, cross tabs, and correlation were used in the adopted statistical methods.

10. Analysis and Discussion of Result

The study had targeted a sample of 110 respondents out of 165. The examination assembled data from 110 individuals, with a reaction pace of 66.7 percent. Table 1 summarizes the respondents' demographic profiles for the study.

Table 10.1.1 Demographical Profile of the respondents

Demographical Profile		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	76	69.09
	Female	34	30.91
Age (In Years)	20-30	32	29.09
	30-40	41	37.27
	40-50	23	20.91
	Above 50	14	12.73
	5-10	42	38.18
Academic Experience (In Years)	10-20	31	28.18
	20-30	26	23.64
	Above 30	11	10.00
	Ph.D.	45	40.91
Highest Qualification	Post Graduate	39	35.45
	Graduate	26	23.64
	Professor	14	12.73
Academic Position	Associate Professor	41	37.27
	Assistant Professor	32	29.09
	Others	23	20.91

10.2. Reliability Analysis

The reliability test was applied to the collected data. A reliability analysis test is done with the stipulation that the variable is supposed to be reliable and can be considered for study if the value of Cronbach alpha (α) is greater than 0.60. The corollary of the reliability analysis test demonstrated the way that all the questions of the questionnaire could be supposed to genuinely deserve being research instruments and in this manner appropriate to be utilized as measuring instruments.

Table-10.2.1 : Reliability Analysis

Variable	No of items	Cronbach alpha (α)	Information
Reward and remuneration	6	0.918	Reliable
Professional Development	5	0.938	Reliable
Communication	3	0.843	Reliable
Work-Life Balance	4	0.891	Reliable
Leadership	6	0.935	Reliable
Employee Retention	6	0.907	Reliable

The corollary of the reliability analysis testutilizing SPSS above shows that every one of these variables of thequestionnaireinstruments has areliability value that serves the purpose and is assertedreliable because Cronbach’s Alpha sign is more than 0.60.

10.2.2. Correlation Analysis

If the coefficient of correlation between two variables is greater than 0.5, it is said that they arecorrelated. One of the independent predictor variables must be excluded from the analysis if there is a correlation. **Table 10.2.2** shows the mean scores based on the weighted average method.

Among all the factors, leadership behavior has got highest mean value of 4.0545 (S.D. =0.88656). This implies representatives are profoundly happy and satisfied with the factor practices by thecollege and all the employees acknowledge it. From the characteristics ofthe data, it is observed that the data of continuing professional development (Mean = 3.9000, S. D. = 1.01322) and open communication(Mean = 3.9182, S. D. = 0.97803)are highly deviated from the mean among all other factors. Thisstatistical evidence implies that these two factors involved in the practice of the college are not appropriate for all employees of the institutions. As a result, the college should reevaluate its communication and practices for professional development. In contrast, the data of workload (Mean = 4.1182, S. D. = 0.82096) and reward and remuneration (Mean = 4.0455, S. D. = 0.88189) have been found less deviated fromthe mean. These statistics indicate that the college has been successfully distributing equivalent burdensand providing fairwards and remuneration, whichare appreciated and valued by all levels of the employees.

Table-10.2.2 : Mean, Standard Deviation, and Correlation Coefficient

Correlations								
Variables	Mean	Std Dev.	ER	RR	CPP	C	WL	L
Employee Retention(ER)	4.0545	.87615	1	.911**	.823**	.883**	.897**	.894**
Reward and remuneration(RR)	4.0455	.88189	.911**	1	.796**	.866**	.880**	.877**
Continuous Professional Development(CPP)	3.9000	1.01322	.823**	.796**	1	.871**	.808**	.915**
Communication (C)	3.9182	.97803	.883**	.866**	.871**	1	.812**	.883**
Work-Life Balance (WL)	4.1182	.82096	.897**	.880**	.808**	.812**	1	.886**
Leadership (L)	4.0545	.88656	.894**	.877**	.915**	.883**	.886**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In the table, a significant positive and strong correlation was found for employee retention in relationship with reward and remuneration policy ($r = 0.911$, $p < 0.01$), with continuous professional development ($r = 0.823$, $p < 0.01$), with open and clear communication ($r = 0.883$, $p < 0.01$), with Work-Life Balance ($r = 0.897$, $p < 0.01$), and with leadership ($r = 0.894$, $p < 0.01$). This significant correlation indicates that these factors have a strong influence on the employee retention policy of the college. Moreover, a positive and strong correlation was found between reward and remuneration policy, continuous professional development, open and clear communication, Work-Life Balance, and leadership which implies the college should develop and adopt a policy that has complete synchronization among those factors.

This significant correlation demonstrates that these variables influence the college's employee retention strategy. In addition, a positive and strong correlation was found between the institute's reward and remuneration policy, ongoing professional development, open and transparent communication, Work-Life Balance, and leadership. This indicates that the college ought to develop and implement a policy that synchronizes all of these aspects completely.

10.2.3. Regression Model

Multiple regression is a statistical approach used to obtain the value of a measure of various predictor variables on an explanatory variable. It is the instantaneous amalgamation of numerous factors to evaluate how and to what level the dependent variable is affected by various predictor variables. Regression is used to determine the value of a dependent variable based on the value of two or more predictor variables. In this study, we checked the impact of selected variables on the dependent variable.

The statistical method known as multiple regression is used to determine the effect of various predictor variables on an explanatory variable. It is the instantaneous fusion of numerous factors to determine how and to what extent the dependent variable is affected by various predictor variables. Based on the value of two or more predictor variables, regression is used to calculate the value of a dependent variable. In this study, we checked the impact of selected variables (reward and remuneration policy, ongoing professional development, open and transparent communication, Work-Life Balance, and leadership) on the dependent variable (employee retention).

Table 10.2.3.1 Regression Analysis

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. F Change
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	
1	.946 ^a	.895	.890	.29068	.895	177.251	5	104	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), L, RR, C, WL, CPP									
b. Dependent Variable: ER									

Table 10.2.3.2 Anova Table

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	74.885	5	14.977	177.251	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.788	104	.084		
	Total	83.673	109			
a. Dependent Variable: ER						
b. Predictors: (Constant), L, RR, C, WL, CPP						

Table 10.2.3.3 Coefficient

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.053	.145		.370	.712		
	RR	.304	.082	.306	3.710	.000	.149	6.717
	CPP	-.052	.074	-.061	-.710	.479	.139	7.198
	C	.247	.072	.276	3.438	.001	.156	6.394
	WL	.323	.083	.303	3.910	.000	.169	5.932
	L	.167	.106	.169	1.573	.119	.087	11.444
a. Dependent Variable: ER								

Table-10.2.3.1 shows that 89.0% of employee retention is explained by all independent variables, such as reward and remuneration policy, ongoing professional development, open and transparent communication, work-life balance, and leadership. However, the model's significance is demonstrated in the ANOVA table. According to Table 10.2.3.3 regression equation of employee retention satisfaction is :

Employee Retention = 0.53 + 0.304 (Reward and remuneration) - 0.052 (Continuous professional development) + 0.247 (Open and transparent communication) + 0.323 (Work-Life Balance) + 0.167 (leadership).

The results from the analysis showed there is a positive relationship between all the Employee Relationship practices and employee retention of employees except one i.e. opportunity for Continuous professional development.

11. Strategies for Building Positive Employee Relationships in the Education Sector

1. **Initiatives to Increase Employee Engagement** : Higher education institutions (HEI) may be able to amplify their efforts to enhance employee engagement initiatives by capitalizing on their successes in establishing effective grievance redressal mechanisms and transparent communication. Higher education institutes (HEI) can cultivate a sense of belonging, ownership, and shared purpose among their workforce by encouraging open dialogue, soliciting feedback, and recognizing contributions.
2. **Collaboration in Decision-Making** : Expanding on the association's accomplishments in esteeming representative info and points of view, higher education institutions (HEI) could additionally systematize collaboration in making decisions. Higher education institutions (HEI) can harness collective insights, foster innovation, and drive organizational excellence by involving employees in strategic planning, policy formulation, and organizational governance.
3. **Initiatives for Professional Development** : To additional sustain the ability inside its positions; higher education institutions (HEI) could consider upgrading their proficient improvement programs. To keep employees at the forefront of industry advancement, best practices in mentoring, coaching, and upskilling initiatives may be revealed through comparative analyses with leading organizations.
4. **Policies that improve and encourage a better work-life balance** : Higher education institutions (HEIs) could look into implementing family-friendly policies, wellness programs, and flexible work arrangements, building on the positive perceptions of work-life balance already in place. Insights into innovative practices that prioritize employee prosperity and well-being

while maintaining organizational efficiency may be acquired by comparing them to industry pioneers.

5. **Comprehensive Communication Stages** : It is essential to emphasize inclusive communication strategies. Higher education institutions (HEI) could use technology to develop platforms that make transparent communication, feedback, collaboration, and coordinated effort easier at all levels of the hierarchy. Gaining from industry benchmarks can help recognize cutting-edge specialized apparatuses and rehearses that encourage hierarchical attachment.
6. **Continuous Feedback and Acknowledgment** : Implementing robust feedback mechanisms and recognition programs can further enhance employee morale and engagement. Higher education institutions (HEI) can cultivate a culture of appreciation and a continuous environment by improving their performance appraisal systems, reward mechanisms, and employee recognition initiatives by benchmarking them against peers in the industry who are known for their focus on employees.

12. Strategies for Retaining Employees at Various Levels of Management

The possible retention strategies are depicted in Figure-1 below and used to keep workers at all three levels of management, namely the Top, Middle, and Lower levels, as each level calls for a unique treatment due to the difference in designation and hierarchical status and an assortment of pay scales.

3 Levels		
Lower Level	Middle Level	Top Level
Acknowledging and increasing a work well accomplished Acclaiming professionals and personal achievements Offering benefits Offering incentives and perks Providing workplace amenities	Acknowledging and increasing a work well accomplished Providing various benefit programs for family Giving satisfactory workplace Facilitating opportunities for self-improvement and career advancement	Increasing Work-Life Efficiency Recognize the needs of employees Promoting Professional and Personal Growth and Development Create a trusting environment Hiring the right people

13. Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, there is strong evidence that employee relationships positively impact employee retention and job satisfaction. Employee retention is correlated with the strength of interpersonal relationships. There are numerous approaches to improving the representatives' relationship in this review. The best method for further developing representative relations is open and transparent correspondence. In an association, there should be a correspondence between one another. Consequently, they can achieve the same objective. There will continuously be a contention between the colleagues or among managers and workers in the association. Because employers can better understand their employees' strengths and weaknesses, the work becomes easier after communication. Based on their knowledge and skills, employees can be assigned jobs that are right for them. Employees place a high value on top management because it is essential to promote human values and maintain positive relationships with them. An organization can benefit from the efforts of skilled leaders and professionals in human resources to foster and maintain a spirit of cooperation. At the point when the pioneers generally continue upholding and executing this soul in the whole association, then the whole association will systematically assimilate a similar soul. Subsequently, it will end up being the association's perspective.

When they are satisfied with their work, representatives are motivated to work. Large portions of the representatives are persuaded to work when their top administration has valued their work. Additionally, the institute offers excellent benefits or rewards to its employees. Institutes will soon use gainsharing to reward productive teams. To reap the rewards, employees will do their best to complete all tasks. Fortunately, this strategy has helped improve relationships with employees. Motivated employees will drive the institute's growth. Assuming that an institute has positive employee relations, the battles will be less because the differentiations between the employer and employee have not increased any expansive openings. While employee relations have been improved, the way of life in the work environment will turn out to be better, and individuals need to work in a work environment that has a decent culture. Employees will naturally comply with the institute's guidelines and standards when there is a good relationship in the group.

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